

Economic and Feasibility Analysis of a Hybrid Micro Hydro /PV Generation System in Egypt

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Abstract

This study explores the feasibility of utilizing a hybrid micro hydro and photovoltaic (PV) power system for inexpensive electricity generation that meets the energy demands of a small recreational area located in Nubian village, Aswan,. In this framework, the optimal configurations are identified to enhance both the efficiency and economic viability of the hybrid proposed system, taking into account load energy needs, available resources (solar and water). The operation and installation costs of the proposed system are analyzed through simulations conducted using the Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewables (HOMER), incorporating inputs such as solar radiation, stream flow, and each component costs. A sensitivity analysis is performed utilizing HOMER.

1. Introduction

A key motivation behind economic development is the enhancement of the electricity sector, as it significantly contributes to modern society. With population growth, increased human comfort levels, and industrialization, the demand for electricity is rapidly escalating worldwide, showing an annual growth rate of 4%. Consequently, many researchers focus on methods to conserve or generate electricity. Most of the world's energy is sourced from fossil fuels, which are finite and ultimately depleting, making it impossible to meet all energy needs with them. This situation results in substantial exhaust emissions, with traditional generating systems responsible for more than 75% of global CO₂ emissions [1-3].

Small hydropower plants typically utilize a "run of river" approach, which does not involve significant water impounding and thus does not necessitate the creation of large dams and reservoirs. Nevertheless, the energy generated is contingent upon the

volume of available water and the fluctuations in flow throughout the year. In several developing nations in Africa, the hydro resource is least favorable during the dry season, coinciding with a period of abundant solar resource. Effectively harnessing the synergies between these two energy sources is essential for ensuring a steady electricity supply in optimal locations. The Nubian village in Aswan serves as a compelling case study due to its advantageous hydro and solar resources.

Numerous PV-hybrid systems have been suggested in the past for providing electricity to remote regions or grid-connected locations. Many renewable energy systems have been studied by researchers to reduce costs and address the unpredictable nature of renewable resources through various modeling and optimization tools. A total of eighteen software tools, including Hybrid2, iHOGA, RETScreen, and HOMER, are reviewed in [4], where HOMER is identified as a fast-processing and user-friendly software widely utilized for feasibility assessments of hybrid renewable energy initiatives. In [5], HOMER is conducted to assess the use of for modeling a wind-diesel hybrid system aimed at meeting the annual load demand of 3512 MWh for residential buildings in Saudi Arabia, and compares its costs and carbon emissions with those of a standalone diesel generator system. In [6], a feasibility study is undertaken for electrifying isolated areas in Ethiopia using a hybrid power system (HPS) that includes solar, wind turbine, and fuel cells, with results contrasted against previously analyzed models (PV, wind turbine, and genset) regarding costs and carbon emissions. A control system has been developed for a PV/battery system utilizing MATLAB, aimed at minimizing peak load demands in an underwater tunnel located in Canada, and it has been further analyzed in Homer to determine the economic advantages of this control setup [7]. To provide electricity to a remote village in Karnataka, India, a HPS incorporating solar/wind/diesel was modeled in [8] to assess the influence of variable intermittency on the renewable energy system and to suggest the most cost-effective design for energy provision. In [9], a HPS that includes PV, wind, diesel, and batteries was modeled to identify optimized solutions for electrifying the buildings in varying climatic conditions of Iran. In [10], six cities in Turkey were analyzed to evaluate the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for grid-connected versus stand-alone PV systems designed to meet an annual energy demand of 2500 kWh, revealing that the PV grid-connected system is more cost-effective than the off-grid stand-alone alternative. HPS including

PV, batteries, and biodiesel was studied in [11] for a university in northern Ghana, and its costs were compared to grid prices using Homer, with simulation results indicating that the cost per unit of electricity from the hybrid system is 2% lower than that of grid electricity. The socio-economic benefits and potential of a HPS of PV/wind/diesel/battery were explored in [12] for a community with a peak demand of 51.52 kW and a daily energy demand of 242.56 kWh in Bangladesh by HOMER. An optimized and cost-effective design for electrifying a domestic community and agricultural farm in the small village of Layyah district, Pakistan, utilizing a hybrid energy source of biomass and PV was proposed in [13], with Homer simulation results demonstrating that the optimum solution consisted of PV, batteries, biogas, converter of a10 kW, 32, 8 kW, 12 kW. The development and execution of a combined solar and mini-hydro renewable energy system (RES) for the rural community of Muyuka Subdivision was dedicated [14] and assessed the effectiveness of a rural electrification initiative employing hybrid autonomous renewable energy systems. In [15], the assessment, design, modeling, simulation, and evaluation of performance alongside economic viability for a PV and mini hydro system for a rural Ethiopian village were conducted. The MATLAB Simulink toolbox was employed for modeling the renewable energy sources. The system's feasibility was examined using HOMER software. In [16], a study was conducted on a HPS that integrates hydro, PV, and battery technologies in Cameroon. A comparative analysis was performed to validate two methods: HOMER and a genetic algorithm for system optimization.

This study intends to present a hybrid micro hydro/photovoltaic system that is capable of adapting to the seasonal fluctuations in solar and hydro resources. A yearly operational simulation of the system is performed utilizing HOMER software, enabling an evaluation of how each component complements one another. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis is conducted.

2. The Proposed System

Hybrid power generation refers to a system that integrates multiple plants utilizing various energy sources [17–19]. Figure 1 illustrates the configurations of hybrid PV/hydro power plants. The hydroelectric power facility generates renewable energy that is clean and environmentally sustainable [20]. This plant transforms the kinetic

energy of moving water into mechanical energy through the spinning of a hydro turbine, which then drives a generator to create electrical energy. Hydropower is categorized based on its power output, as outlined in Table 1 [21]. Micro hydro power is defined as having a power output of less than 100 kW. To be effective as an electricity-generating resource, the hydro system must possess specific flow and height capabilities, since the power generated by micro hydro is heavily influenced by both the hydro discharge and height of the waterfall [22]. The greater the flow rate and elevation from the setup, the more electrical energy can be produced.

Fig. 1. Configurations of solar/hydro hybrid power plants.

Table 1. Hydro power plants classification according to capacity.

Hydro power	Capacity
Large hydro	>100MW
Medium hydro	15-100 MW
Small hydro	1-15 MW
Mini hydro	100 kW-1 MW
Micro hydro	5kW-100 kW
Pico hydro	<5 kW

3. Cost Assessment of the Proposed System

Numerous elements are considered during the cost assessment [23]:

3.1. The initial project cost

The project's initial expenses (C_o) encompass the machine, building, civil work, and various other costs. The present study assumes that both options will have identical expenditures for construction, civil works, and other variable costs. Therefore, the analysis focused solely on the purchase price of the machine.

3.2. Capital recovery factor (CRF)

CRF is used to determine an equivalent annualized value of the initial investment. The CRF is influenced by the lifespan of the equipment (L) in years and the discount rate (d). It was computed as:

$$CRF = \frac{d(1+d)^L}{(1+d)^L - 1} \quad (1)$$

3.3. Annual Expenses

Annual costs (A_c) consist of operation, fuel, labor, maintenance and other miscellaneous expenses for the specific year. With hydroelectric energy, fuel expenses are negligible since no fuel is required. The analysis indicates that labor expenses and various items were not considered, based on the assumption that these costs remain constant in both scenarios. Consequently, the analysis only included annual operating costs and maintenance costs.

3.4. Discount Rate

The discount rate (d) reflects the value of money today compared to its value in future. This rate influences how cash flows in future are adjusted to correspond with their present worth. The discount rate is always expected to exceed the bank interest rate (IR). bank IR represents the least return available from depositing funds into a bank.

3.5. Annual Life Cycle Cost (A_{LCC})

A_{LCC} represents the current value of all costs associated with a particular choice over its lifespan. To calculate this cost, the present value of annual expenses is combined with the initial investment. These annual expenses include maintenance, energy, labor, and other related costs. A_{LCC} is frequently utilized when comparing two options with similar operational characteristics but varying lifespans, as described in Eq. (2).

$$A_{LCC} = (C_o \text{ } CRF) + A_c \quad (2)$$

3.6. Annual energy production

The yearly energy output (A_e) was determined by multiplying the energy generated per hour by the total number of hours of produced energy in a year.

3.7. Cost per unit of generated electricity

Equation (3) was utilized to compute the electricity generated cost per unit (C). was calculated by multiplying the energy generated per hour by the number of hours per year during which energy can be produced. A_e was determined by multiplying the energy produced each hour by the total number of hours in a year which energy can be generated.

$$C = A_{LCC} / A_e \quad (3)$$

4. Metrological Data

For this analysis, a small recreational area located in the Nubian village of Aswan has been chosen. Its coordinates are 24°05'20"N 32°53'59"E. Solar data for the Nubian village in Aswan was acquired from NASA, with a latitude and longitude of 24°05'20"N and of 32°53'59"E respectively, showing an annual average solar radiation of 6.49 kWh/m²/day. Monthly solar radiation (SR) data is illustrated in Figure 2. The total daily energy requirement is 165 kWh, with a peak demand of 23 kW. Typically, a hydroelectric facility produces a few hundred kilowatts of power, often using a run-of-river method. This method is appropriate for regions with low discharge hydro resources. It was not feasible to determine the flow rate based on rainfall runoff patterns due to the significant data needs that were unavailable during this study. The annual flow rate used in the simulation can be found in Figure 3. The hourly load profile is displayed in Figure 4.

Fig. 2. Monthly SR.

Fig. 3. The annually average flow rate variation.

Fig. 4. Hourly load profile for all months.

5. HOMER Pro Software

Power generation technologies, both renewable and traditional, can be modeled through HOMER. Visual representations help in identifying both market opportunities and challenges for each micro power technology. HOMER facilitates the understanding of the relationships between different conventional, renewable, and hybrid systems along with end-use demand. Taking into account the availability and practicality of RE sources in the area; a HPS has been designed that incorporates micro hydro, solar PV systems, and battery storage. The proposed system is illustrated in Figure 4 using HOMER. The technical and economic parameters of the PV, hydro, converter, and battery employed in the model are outlined in Table 2 and Table 3.

Fig. 4. Proposed Micro hydro/PV system.

Table 2. Technical parameters of hybrid PV hydro system components.

Component	PV array	Hydro	Battery
Technical parameters	1 kWp De-rating factor=0.9 Inverter efficiency= 96%	Rated power= 10 kW Design flow rate =70 L/s; Head =20 m; Efficiency =80% Pipe head loss= 15%	Minimum SOC =0.2; Throughput =2830 kWh Nominal Capacity=2.4 kWh Maximum charge current = 68.4 A Round trip efficiency=0.85

Table 3. Economical parameters of hybrid PV hydro system components.

Cost	PV array	Battery	Hydro	Inverter
Initial capital	2500 \$/kW	170 \$/kWh	2500 \$/kW	500 \$/kW
O&M	10 \$/kW	20 \$/kW	10 \$/kW	5 \$/kW
Replacement	2500 \$/kW	170 \$/ kWh	1500 \$/kW	500 \$/kW
Life time (years)	25	5	25	10

6. Results and Discussion

HOMER is utilized to identify the optimal system configuration through an economic and environmental assessment relevant to the chosen site in Nubian village, Aswan. A sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the system's performance by altering variables that have a direct effect on the operational characteristics of hybrid systems. The results were classified into categories related to technical, economic, environmental factors. For the economic aspects, NPC, LCOE, initial capital (IC), and operational cost (OPC) is examined for each scenario. Likewise, the technical aspects included energy production (EP), unmet electric load (UL), excess electricity (EE), and capacity shortage (CS). The environmental aspects covered emissions of unburned hydrocarbons, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, particulate matter, sulfur and nitrogen oxides.

The optimal configuration for the hybrid system derived from the simulation analysis incorporates a combination of PV, battery, and hydro systems. The energy output from the PV and hydro turbine amounts to 21,724 kWh/yr and 61,358 kWh/yr, respectively, as displayed in Table 4. The optimal system comprises of a 10.2 kW PV array, a 5.49 kW hydro turbine with a nominal battery capacity of 91.7 kWh, and a 16.5 kW converter. The annual OPC is \$1,945, resulting in a cost of electricity (COE) of \$0.113/kWh and a NPC of \$125,918, as shown in Table 5. Figure 5 illustrates the monthly PV and hydro generated power. The system features a 10.2 kW PV installation, which plays a significant role in meeting energy demands during sunny

conditions. The battery bank, with a capacity of 91.7 kWh, aids in storing excess solar energy throughout the day for nighttime or cloudy day usage, thus ensuring a continuous energy supply when PV and hydro generation fall short. The hydro capacity implies that the hydropower can produce up to 5.49 kW, given that the water flow and head height are sufficient. Hydropower offers a reliable energy source, enhancing the fluctuating nature of solar energy. The total annual expenses for the proposed system are US\$11,638, which covers the OPC associated with the hybrid energy system as indicated in Table 6. This includes maintenance for the PV and hydro equipment and batteries, as well as replacement costs for battery parts as time goes on. OPC also covers cleaning the panels, managing hydro channels, and addressing repairs. The combination of these components aims to balance the renewable sources; since solar energy is intermittent and highly dependent on weather conditions and daylight, while hydro provides a more consistent power output, together they ensure a reliable energy supply. Figure 6 presents the cash flow summary for the optimal HPS.

Table 4. Technical results of PV/hydro system.

Quantity	Value	Units
Excess Electricity	20,213	kWh/yr
Unmet Electric Load	37.3	kWh/yr
Capacity Shortage	59.6	kWh/yr
Production Summary		
Component	Production (kWh/yr)	%
PV	21,724	26.1
Hydro	61,358	73.9
Total	83,083	100

Table 5. Net Present Costs of PV/ battery/ hydro scheme.

Name	Capital (\$)	Operating (\$)	Replacement (\$)	Salvage (\$)	Total (\$)
PV	29,119	1,260	0.00	0.00	30,379
Battery	15,200	8,223	25,819	0.00	49,241
Converter	12,079	1,307	8,344	-914.47	20,815
Hydro Gen	25,000	10,819	0.00	0.00	35,819
System	81,397	21,609	34,163	-914.47	136,255

Fig. 5. Monthly production of electric power.

Table 6. Annual Cost of PV/battery/hydro scheme.

Name	Capital (\$)	Operating (\$)	Replacement (\$)	Salvage (\$)	Total (\$)
PV	2,691	116.47	0.00	0.00	2,808
Battery	1,405	760.00	2,386	0.00	4,551
Converter	1,116	120.79	771.25	- 84.52	1,924
Hydro Gen	2,311	1,000	0.00	0.00	3,311
System	7,523	1,997	3,158	-84.52	12,594

Fig. 6. Cash flow summary of PV/battery/hydro scheme.

Figure 7 illustrates hourly charts depicting the power output of the proposed PV/battery/hydro system. It indicates the correlation between the power produced by these sources and the power needed by the load, as well as the energy input to the battery. The PV generator generates electricity throughout the year, operating for a total of 4,380 hours and achieving a peak power output of 11 kW. Hydropower production tends to be more consistent, relying on water flow and reservoir conditions. The curve may fluctuate based on rainfall or seasonal stream flow

variations. The load power illustrates the electricity demands of consumers. The load curve changes throughout the day and year. Battery Input Power indicates how much energy is being stored in the battery. This is vital for balancing generation with demand. During the charging phase, when generation surpasses the load, the excess energy is used to recharge the battery. In the discharging phase, when the load exceeds generation, the battery provides power to meet the demand. During times of peak generation, surplus energy can recharge the battery. When demand surpasses generation, the battery can deliver power to fill the gap.

Fig. 7. Load, PV, hydro and battery input power variations over the year.

The power curve illustrating the discrepancies between unmet load and total load power fluctuations over the year offers valuable insights into energy demand trends and aids in efficient energy management. Unmet Load refers to energy usage that is not directly tracked or recorded through conventional metering techniques. The overall load power generally fluctuates throughout the year due to various factors like seasonal variations, daily consumption patterns, and economic activities. Figure 8 displays the power curve for the total electrical load provided and the unmet electrical load.

Fig. 8. Load electrical power and unmet load variation over the year

The input power curve of a battery depicts the flow of power into the battery over time, as shown in Fig. 9. This curve is essential for grasping how efficiently a battery accumulates energy and reacts to different generation and load scenarios. When renewable generation sources like PV or hydro exceed the demand for power, the excess energy is directed to charge the battery, represented as a positive value on the curve. The input power levels will vary according to the availability of generation. During times when generation matches load demand, the battery may not receive any input power, leading to a flat section on the curve at zero. If the load demand surpasses the generation, the battery will discharge to provide the necessary power. The output power from the hydro power plant is illustrated in Fig. 10, indicating that the hydro power plant generates about 7 kW throughout the year.

Fig. 9. Battery input power variation over the year.

Fig. 10. Output power of hydro power plant.

Sensitivity variables such as hydro head, solar reserve, and wind reserve can be analyzed, as shown in Table 7 using HOMER. Figure 11 presents the relationship between UL and total NPC at $H = 5$ m. Figure 12 illustrates the UL against total net present cost at $H = 5$ m and $H = 10$ m, with both solar reserve and hydro reserve set at 20%. The NPC is lower at $H = 5$ m compared to $H = 10$ m. Consequently, the optimal scenario occurs when $H = 10$ m, with solar reserve at 20% and hydro reserve at 20%. The relationship between PV size and total net present cost in the optimal case is depicted in Fig. 13, showing that PV size increases with the NPC. Figure 14

demonstrates how hydro head relates to total net present cost and unmet load, revealing that both unmet load and total NPC decrease as hydro head increases.

Table 7. Sensitivity Variables.

Head (m)	Solar Reserve (%)	Wind Reserve (%)
20	80	20
5	50	50
10	20	80
15		
25		
30		

Fig. 11. UL vs total NPC at H= 5 m.

Fig. 12. UL vs total NPC at optimal variables H=10 m, solar reserve = 20%, hydro reserve = 20%.

Fig. 13. PV size vs total net present cost at optimal variables $H=10$ m, solar reserve = 20%, hydro reserve = 20%.

Fig. 14. Hydro head vs total NPC and UL.

7. Conclusion

Solar photovoltaic systems and hydropower generators are crucial for harnessing renewable energy. These technologies have significantly enhanced energy efficiency by enabling independent power use in homes and businesses.

Understanding the power curve of PV and hydro systems with battery input is essential for optimizing energy management, ensuring reliability, and enhancing the sustainability of the energy supply. Balancing these elements effectively can lead to a robust and efficient power system. To electrify the Nubian village in Aswan, this research intends to provide a study, analysis, design, and model for a hybrid

hydraulic/photovoltaic generation system. A techno-economic and environmental evaluation was conducted utilizing the HOMER simulation software to identify the best system setup for the chosen remote region. The energy output from the PV and hydro turbine amounts to 21,724 kWh/yr and 61,358 kWh/yr, respectively. The optimal system comprises of a 10.2 kW PV array, a 5.49 kW hydro turbine with a nominal battery capacity of 91.7 kWh, and a 16.5 kW converter. The annual OPC is \$1,945, resulting in a cost of electricity (COE) of \$0.113/kWh and a NPC of \$125,918. To evaluate system performance, a sensitivity analysis was carried out by modifying variables that directly impact on the behavior of hybrid systems. Sensitivity variables such as hydro head, solar reserve, and wind reserve can be analyzed. The optimal scenario occurs when hydro head at 10 m, with solar reserve at 20% and hydro reserve at 20%.

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